

1000G projection

1. Goal

This document describes how to project your dataset into the firsts 5 principal components (PCs) computed in 1000G Phase3 in order to calibrate the PRS. The following sections describe how to perform that.

2. Software

In order to extract, convert and perform the projection, the following software are required :

- plink1.9 : <https://www.cog-genomics.org/plink/1.9/>
- flashPCA2 : <https://github.com/gabraham/flashpca>

3. Files

The following files are needed in order to perform the projection :

- 1000G_pca_variants.txt : contains the variants to use to perform the projection. These variants were selected based on an imputation quality of 0.8 in all datasets and merged with the 1000G Phase3 selected variants (MAF>0.01, no ambiguous variants, no indels, not in long range LD or problematic regions) followed by a pruning step. This file contains 84,035 variants in GRCh38 assembly with ID of the form : chr:pos:ref:alt.
- 1000G_pca_variants_a1_allele.txt : contains the 1000G Phase3 A1 allele (i.e. minor allele) that will be used to convert the dataset into a plink format, forcing the minor allele to be the same as the 1000G Phase3 one, which is very important for the projection.
- 1000G_pca_variants_meansd.txt : the mean/sd file that will be used by flashPCA2 to project your data
- 1000G_pcva_variants_load.txt : the loading file that will be used by flashPCA2 to project your data4. Steps to project your dataset

4. Projection

4.1. Extract needed variants

Using the list of 84,035 variants provided in the file '1000G_pca_variants.txt', extract all of them from your imputed data. This list contains variants with an imputation quality above 0.8 in all datasets so you should find all of them in your data. Depending on your input format, this step could be done using bcftools or plink (but if already in plink format, check if your data contains the imputed best guessed genotypes without any filtering).

4.2. Convert into plink format

Assuming you have a vcf/bcf input file resulting from step 1, the second step is to convert it into a plink bed/bim/fam format using plink1.9 (or plink2 but you should stick to the bed/bim/fam format and not pgen/psam/pvar format in order to be compatible with flashPCA2 software). We use all best guessed genotypes without any filter and we force the A1 allele (i.e. minor allele in plink format) to be the same one as the 1000G dataset which is mandatory to correctly project your samples.

Example of plink command line (without any memory/threads parameters which will be set accordingly to your resources) :

```
plink --bfile input.vcf.gz --a1-allele 1000G_pca_variants_a1_allele.txt 2 1 --make-bed --out output_for_projection
```

You should have a bed/bim/fam files and in the log file the following messages meaning that you have all the variants with the forcing A1 allele without any missing data :

Total genotyping rate is exactly 1.

--a1-allele: 84035 assignments made.

4.3 Projection of your samples

The final step is to perform the projection of your samples into the 1000G Phase3 PCs. In order to do that, we use flashPCA2 with the following command line using the output of the previous step (with XX threads in order to speed-up the process and seed YYYY to be able to reproduce the projection) :

```
flashPCA2 --bfile output_for_projection --numthreads XX --project --seed YYYY --inmeansd 1000G_pca_variants_meansd.txt --inload 1000G_pcva_variants_load.txt --outpoj output_projection_1000G.tsv
```

The output file should contain all of your samples projected in the firsts 5 PCs of 1000G Phase3. This file will be used for the PRS calibration.